

Review

Restricted access to pasture and inadequate grazing in ruminants and equines

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1 Executive summary

Pasture access allows ruminants and equines to graze or browse plants, and also provides opportunities to express a large behavioural repertoire, generally increasing animal welfare. Indeed, animals at pasture spend more time moving and exploring, can express social facilitation with their conspecifics, can have improved lying comfort and better social interactions with conspecifics. Pasture access also improves expression of feeding behaviour by increasing the time spent foraging and allows animals to choose their preferred feed. Finally, several benefits on health parameters have been reported, such as a decrease of locomotion disorders, skin lesions, mastitis, and also the possibility of self-medication against parasitism. When access to pasture is restricted (no access at all or no access after a period of grazing), there is generally an increase of abnormal behaviours, which may be associated with changes in physiological and health parameters, indicative of impaired welfare. However, pasture access for ruminants and equines may also present some risks. Nutritional deficiency may occur depending on several factors such as climate, soil properties, variation in feed quality or botanical composition of pasture that can lead to insufficient forage intake (quality or quantity), and also the presence of toxic plants. Thermal stress is another major issue due to extreme hot and cold weather conditions. Ruminants and equines may also be at risk regarding locomotory and health disorders (e.g. parasitism). Finally, to ensure adequate access to pasture, recommendations are provided on feed, water, shelter, disease prevention and walking tracks and roads.

2 Foreword

The European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare for Ruminants and Equines (EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines*) develops and disseminates knowledge and tools to assist the Competent Authorities (CAs) in performing better official controls and enforcing EU animal welfare rules. It covers a range of farm animal species including those used for dairy (cows, goats, sheep, buffaloes, horses) and meat (cattle, sheep, goats, deer, horses) production and ruminants and equines kept for other purposes. Based on discussions with CAs, EURCAW *Ruminants & Equines* identified restricted access to pasture and grazing as an important issue for ruminant and equine welfare. The present document reviews the available evidence and proposes recommendations to avoid these welfare issues.

3 Introduction and definitions

Ruminants and equines are herbivorous animals. Cattle, sheep or horses graze pasture plants (essentially grass), deer also like to browse, whereas goats and large camelids have a more eclectic feeding behaviour and also browse trees and shrubs (Broom & Fraser, 2007; Kilgour, 2019; Mohammed, Animut, Urge, & Assefa, 2020; Waring, 2002). Grazing and browsing are natural feeding behaviours for ruminants and equines, and preventing such behaviours can negatively impact their welfare.

Grazing, defined as *"to consume predominantly herbaceous forage in situ by animals"*, requires access to pasture, i.e. *"a type of grazing management unit enclosed and separated from other areas by fencing or other barriers and devoted to the production of forage for harvest primarily by grazing"* (Allen et al., 2011). This review focuses on pasture-based systems and therefore not on outdoor access without grazing/browsing opportunities. There are three types of pasture-based systems (EFSA¹, 2023):

1. **Exercise-paddock**, i.e. a restricted access to small pastures during spring/summer;
2. **Pasture-grazing and housing**, i.e. where pasture contributes significantly to the dietary ration of animals during spring/summer;
3. **Pasture-grazing only**, i.e. where animals are kept outdoors exclusively or for most of the year, with or without access to a shelter or resting area.

Pasture provides not only the possibility to graze, but also space for physical activity, exploration and social interactions (e.g. by allowing animals to choose social partners or subordinate individuals to escape easily). Ruminants and equines are social animals, forming groups including complex interactions between individuals (Keeling & Gonyou, 2001). For animals housed individually, like horses in single boxes, pasture access is the only opportunity to fully interact with conspecifics.

When kept indoors, animals have a strong motivation to access outdoor areas, even if the area is without grass or leaves to ingest (cattle: Smid, Burgers, Weary, Bokkers, & von Keyserlingk, 2019; sheep: Stubsjøen et al., 2022; Piirsalu, Kaart, Nutt, Marcone, & Arney, 2020; goats: Seyfi, 2019), or without conspecifics (horses: Lee, Floyd, Erb, & Houpt, 2011). This suggests that animals are motivated to access outdoor areas providing more space. However, access to pasture provides additional benefits, allowing grazing and facilitating the expression of lying, standing, walking and oestrus behaviours in cattle (Smid, Weary, & von Keyserlingk, 2020). Moreover, it was shown that farms where cows had access to pasture for less than two months per year were at a higher risk of poor welfare (e.g. lameness, integument lesion) (EFSA, 2023). Thus, access to pasture, which combines additional space allowance and the possibility to express natural behaviours, improves the welfare of all ruminants and equines. This is contingent on the

¹ European Food Safety Authority

challenges of outdoor access, which can have an impact on animal health and welfare (e.g. parasitism, heat waves), are dealt with.

In Europe, there is a large variation in the time that dairy cows are allowed access to pasture and, in general, farming systems with access to pasture are decreasing. Focusing on dairy cattle (the most common farmed ruminant species), some countries in Northern Europe (e.g. Norway, Finland, Sweden) have welfare legislation that requires outdoor housing for several weeks a year (at least in some systems). Western Europe (e.g. Ireland) has seasonal grass-based systems. In Central Europe, access to grazing is less common (e.g. in Denmark, Germany, Austria) but still well practiced in most Western European countries (e.g. the Netherlands, Belgium, France). Eastern (e.g. Poland, Slovenia, Estonia) and Southern Europe (e.g. Portugal, Spain, Greece, Italy) generally have a low level of grazing, due to an increase in herd size and weather conditions in the South (van den Pol-van Dasselhaar, Hennessy, & Isselstein, 2020; EFSA, 2023).

Data for other species are difficult to find but one can think that the trend observed in dairy cattle is the same for other dairy animals. In this review, beef cattle, small ruminants, equines, deer, llamas and alpacas are also considered, as well as large camels as their recent introduction to dairy farms in the EU - with grazing and feeding conditions different from the camel's natural environment - poses a risk to their welfare (Padalino & Faye, 2024; Smits, Joosten, Faye, & Burger, 2023).

In the EU, there is no legislation (at the date of publication of the present document) on access to pasture for ruminants and equines, except for animals kept in organic production systems. The EU Regulation 2018/848 on organic production and labelling of organic products states that one principle of the organic production is to “[...] *enhance the immune system and strengthen the natural defence against diseases, including regular exercise and access to open air areas and pastures*” (Chapter II, Article 6, Point I). Moreover, the related annex states that “*livestock shall have permanent access to open air areas that allow the animals to exercise, preferably pasture, whenever weather and seasonal conditions and the state of the ground allow, except where restrictions and obligations related to the protection of human and animal health have been imposed on the basis of Union legislation.*”, and that “*the number of livestock shall be limited with a view to minimising overgrazing, poaching of soil, erosion, and pollution caused by animals or by the spreading of their manure.*” (Annex II, Part II, Point 1.7.3 and 1.7.4). Access to pasture is assumed to positively contribute to the welfare of ruminants and equines. In this review, we detail the positive effects of access to pasture and grazing from an animal welfare perspective and the consequences if this is prevented. Moreover, the risks related to pasture access are addressed and recommendations to ensure adequate pasture access for animals are given.

4 What does pasture provide?

Access to pasture for various species of ruminants and monogastric mammals is an environment that allows them to express natural patterns of behaviour but also reduces the risk of injuries and some pathologies. Below, the advantages of grazing will be presented in relation to three main aspects: the physical environment and related behaviours, feeding behaviours, and health. The

advantages of being able to graze will be presented for both ruminants (cattle, sheep, camels and goats) and equines (horses, donkeys).

4.1 Behaviours related to the physical environment

When animals are at pasture, they are more active than in a confined environment, e.g. grazing animals spend more time walking (cattle: Dohme-Meier et al., 2014; sheep: Casamassima et al., 2001). While grazing, animals walk slowly (Broom & Fraser, 2007), which could explain the higher proportion of time spent walking at pasture compared to indoor. For example, camels constantly move to graze in desert areas (Rutagwenda, Lechner-Doll, Schwartz, Schultka, & Von Engelhardt, 1990), referred to as “ambulatory grazing” (Bernard Faye, 2020) and can walk more than 20 km per day. However, space allocated to the animals must be taken into account, e.g. in horses, the time spent moving is related to the size of the pasture: the larger the pasture, the more time spent moving (Maisonpierre et al., 2019).

Larger space availability associated with lower restriction on resource accessibility at pasture (e.g. lying surfaces, grass, scratching surfaces), compared to indoor systems, allow the animals to synchronise their behaviours. For example, cows synchronise their lying behaviour more at pasture than when indoors (Crump, Jenkins, Bethell, Ferris, & Arnott, 2019). Pasture also positively influences lying behaviour allowing different types of postures in dairy cows (e.g. lateral or ventral recumbency) (Krohn & Munksgaard, 1993). Resting comfort is generally better at pasture probably due to larger lying surfaces without obstacles compared to conditions usually encountered indoors. Furthermore, animals at pasture take less time to rise and lie down (cattle: Corazzin, Piasentier, Dovier, & Bovolenta, 2010; Higashiyama, Higashiyama, Ikeda, Komatsu, & Fukasawa, 2013; Wagner et al., 2018) and have less interrupted lying-down movements (cattle: Krohn & Munksgaard, 1993) indicating better lying conditions. Moreover, when at pasture, they do not collide with equipment during lying movement (cattle: Michel, Guatteo, Delezoïde, & Bareille, 2018; Wagner et al., 2018), which reduces the risk of injuries due to collisions. However, at pasture the daily lying time is generally reduced in cows, *“possibly due to the time required for grazing”* (EFSA, 2023). These advantages of comfort and lying behaviour could also be true for other ruminant or equine species, but little is known about lying behaviour at pasture for other species.

Regarding social behaviours, there are fewer agonistic and more positive social behaviours on pasture than for indoor housing or when in a more restricted outdoor area (cattle: Smid, Weary, & von Keyserlingk, 2020; goats: Górecki, Sochacka, & Kaźmierczak, 2020; horses: Majecka & Klawe, 2018).

In general, emotional state is perceived more positively by observers when using qualitative behaviour assessment (cattle: Wagner et al., 2018; goats: Grosso et al., 2016). In horses, pasture access induces a positive cognitive bias (horses: Löckener, Reese, Erhard, & Wöhr, 2016). Human-animal relationships can also be improved with pasture access as shown for horses (Popescu, Lazar, Borda, Blaga Petrean, & Mitrănescu, 2022; Rivera, Benjamin, Nielsen, Shelle, & Zanella, 2002).

4.2 Feeding behaviour

Animals at pasture spend more time feeding than those housed indoors (cattle: Di Grigoli et al., 2019; Dohme-Meier et al., 2014; Roca-Fernández, Ferris, & González-Rodríguez, 2013; horses: Werhahn, Hessel, & Van den Weghe, 2012; camels: Aoun, Atigui, Brahmi, Gherairi, & Hammadi, 2024), suggesting a motivation to perform feeding behaviour most of the day. In horses, the dry matter intake of grass on pasture is greater than the intake of hay in the stalls over the same period, suggesting that grazing stimulates intake (Chavez, Siciliano, & Huntington, 2014; Glunk, Pratt-Phillips, & Siciliano, 2013) whereas, in cows, dry matter intakes are lower at pasture (Dohme-Meier et al., 2014).

When pasture is dietary diversified, it is likely to improve both hedonic (well-being based upon pleasure and comfort seeking) and eudaimonic well-being (well-being stemming from the pursuit of a good life through individual choices) in grazing species (Beck & Gregorini, 2020). Diet diversity through pasture access has the potential to improve eudaimonic well-being in grazing species *"by providing the animals with choice, thus allowing control over the animal's environment and the expression of individuality"* (Beck & Gregorini, 2020). When animals have the opportunity to graze and/or browse diverse vegetation, they select their favourite plants resulting in more time spent consuming some species over others (sheep: EFSA, 2014; Sanon, Kaboré-Zoungrana, & Ledin, 2007; goats: Fedele, Pizzillo, Claps, Morand-Fehr, & Rubino, 1993; horses: Fleurance, Rossignol, & Dumont, 2022; cows : Horadagoda, Fulkerson, Nandra, & Barchia, 2009; camels: Leparmarai, Mwangi, Gluecks, Mutie, & Marquardt, 2018). Moreover, as well as selecting their favourite plant species, they also are selective for parts of a plant. In general, ruminants graze by horizon (i.e. selecting upper leafier parts having a higher nutritional value) (Baumont, Cohen-Salmon, Prache, & Sauvant, 2004; Fonseca, Mezzalira, Bremm, & Carvalho, 2012).

4.3 Health

Many studies report a lower presence of injuries and pathologies in animals that have access to pasture compared to those maintained indoors. It is however difficult to give a minimum time of access to the pasture for this effect to be visible.

Regarding locomotory disorders, grazing cattle have a reduction in hock damage, lameness and claw disorders (Hernandez-Mendo, Keyserlingk, Veira, & Weary, 2007; Loberg, Telezhenko, Bergsten, & Lidfors, 2004; Schenkenfelder & Winckler, 2021), probably because of larger space availability, softer, cleaner and less abrasive ground with cows standing less in manure (Aubé et al., 2022). A study on goats grazing showed less claw overgrowth compared with goats that did not graze on pasture, probably due to prolonged claw contact with hard ground (Sailer et al., 2021). Horses that have access to pasture showed a decrease in lameness, less superficial feet lesions and swollen tendons/joints, and less abnormal hoof horn quality (Popescu et al., 2022, 2019). The improved claw, hoof, and foot health and reduced disorders are likely to apply to sheep and camels, but to our knowledge there is no research on these health aspects at pasture for those species.

In regard to skin lesions, there are usually less injuries for cows at pasture than indoors (Armbrecht, Lambertz, Albers, & Gauly, 2019; Burow, Rousing, Thomsen, Otten, & Sørensen, 2013; Corazzin, Piasentier, Dovier, & Bovolenta, 2010; EFSA, 2009), probably because lying surfaces are softer at pasture and there is less contact with potentially injurious objects (reviewed by Aubé et al., 2022). Similarly, stallions had less hip point and fewer deep body lesions when kept in a group on pasture compared to indoor tie-stall housing (Popescu et al., 2022). However, alopecia can be observed in equines on pasture, which is mainly due to social interactions between animals.

Mastitis prevalence is usually lower in cows at pasture, probably because the lying surfaces are cleaner at pasture (Armbrecht, Lambertz, Albers, & Gauly, 2019; Arnott, Ferris, & O'connell, 2017; EFSA, 2009). One study found that outdoor ewes had lower somatic cell counts in their milk than indoor ewes, higher somatic cell counts in indoor ewes are probably due to suboptimal ventilation and litter contamination from faecal accumulation and teat trampling (Casamassima et al., 2001).

A reduction of incidence of some diseases can be observed at pasture: uterine diseases and dystocia (cattle: Arnott, Ferris, & O'connell, 2017; Michel, Guatteo, Delezoïde, & Bareille, 2018), ocular discharge (goats: Silva Salas, Mondragón-Ancelmo, Jiménez Badillo, Rodríguez Licea, & Napolitano, 2021 ; horses: Popescu et al., 2022), abscesses (goats: Silva Salas, Mondragón-Ancelmo, Jiménez Badillo, Rodríguez Licea, & Napolitano, 2021), dyspnoea, gastric ulcers and colic (horses: Popescu et al., 2019; Ermers, McGilchrist, Fenner, Wilson, & McGreevy, 2023; Hillyer et al., 2002).

Finally, a possible self-medication activity has been observed at pasture in sheep and goats, which are reported to increase their intake of tannin-rich foods when infected with gastrointestinal parasites; tannins have a direct anthelmintic effect and boost immune responses to intestinal parasites (sheep: Juhnke, Miller, Hall, Provenza, & Villalba, 2012; Lisonbee, Villalba, Provenza, & Hall, 2009; goats: Amit et al., 2013).

5 Consequences of preventing pasture access

A restriction in the access to pasture or grazing can increase the expression of undesirable behaviours (stereotypic and agonistic) or abnormal changes in behaviours. For instance, stereotypic behaviours are observed in male dromedary camels housed in individual boxes (Padalino et al., 2014), in cows outside the grazing period after a period of grazing (Corazzin, Piasentier, Dovier, & Bovolenta, 2010), or in horses mainly housed in individual boxes or moved from pasture to a stable (Christie et al., 2006; Ruet et al., 2020). As mentioned above, access to pasture not only provides an opportunity to graze, but also changes the social and physical environment of animals. The changes in behaviour (and particularly undesirable ones) are multifactorial. In horses, aggressive behaviours towards humans also occur when animals are mainly housed in individual boxes or moved from pasture to a stable (Henry, Fureix, Rowberry, Bateson, & Hausberger, 2017; Ruet et al., 2020), and agonistic interactions increase in sheep when moved from pasture to indoor housing (EFSA, 2014). Animals can also be less active when they are moved from pasture to indoor housing (sheep: Casamassima et al., 2001; horses: Ruet

et al., 2020) and horses have a reduced sleep time when moved from pasture to individual housing (Greening & McBride, 2022).

Some changes in physiological and health parameters can also be found. For instance, moving animals from pasture to indoor housing increases plasma cortisol for several weeks in sheep (EFSA, 2014), and increases faecal glucocorticoid metabolites in horses (Marr, Preisler, Farmer, Stefanski, & Krueger, 2020). Intestinal motility can also be reduced (which increases the risk of intestinal impaction) in stabled horses compared to horses at pasture (Williams, Tucker, Green, & Freeman, 2011). In camels, blood cortisol levels were significantly lower after parturition in a pastoral system compared to an indoor system (Atta et al., 2021).

The multiple negative effects observed when moving animals from pasture to indoor housing (whether in group or isolated) support the idea of a general positive effect of access to pasture on animal welfare.

6 Risks at pasture

Despite all the positive effects described above, pasture access and grazing opportunities carries some risks that must be carefully managed. Predation risk will not be dealt with in this review, as it would need a more detailed discussion.

6.1 Feeding disorders

Animals in pasture-based systems can be affected by nutritional or metabolic stressors, since quality and quantity of grazing depend on factors such as climate and physical properties of soil. In addition, variations in nutrient content and palatability of different pasture species across seasons can impact an animal's grazing behaviour and intake (sheep: Fernandez-Turren, Repetto, Arroyo, Pérez-Ruchel, & Cajarville, 2020; Pain, Corkran, Kenyon, Morris, & Kemp, 2014; Tüfekci & Sejian, 2023). There have been documented cases of malnutrition and metabolic disorders (e.g. negative energy balance, ketosis, macro- and micro-nutrient deficiencies) caused by poor forage quality (cattle: Burow, Rousing, Thomsen, Otten, & Sørensen, 2013; EFSA, 2009; Mee & Boyle, 2020; Olmos et al., 2009; sheep: Tüfekci & Sejian, 2023), low phosphorus soils (cattle: Dixon, Anderson, Kidd, & Fletcher, 2020). For example, grass tetany in cattle can occur due to insufficient magnesium intake or impaired magnesium absorption, particularly at the beginning of the grazing season when the grass is young (Littledike, Young, & Beitz, 1981; Martens, 2016). Pastures too rich in nutrients negatively affect the health of large camels, as they digest plants of low nutritional value better, especially those rich in lignin and cellulose (Al-Jassim & Hogan, 2012). In addition, climate and seasonality of resources could result in low grass availability posing risks such as an insufficient or discontinuous energy supply leading to underfeeding (cattle: Mee & Boyle, 2020; sheep: Fernandez-Turren et al., 2020; Pain et al., 2014; Tüfekci & Sejian, 2023; goats: Silva et al., 2022) particularly for dairy cows, which require balanced diets due to their high production levels (these can be managed more effectively by feeding with a total mixed ration (TMR)).

In contrast, another risk for animals is overfeeding, caused by an abundance of grass in temperate climate regions, especially when it is rich in water soluble carbohydrates and non-structural

carbohydrates (horses: Ermers, McGilchrist, Fenner, Wilson, & McGreevy, 2023; Molle, Cannas, & Gregorini, 2022). This can lead, especially in equines, to metabolic disorders such as laminitis (horses: Ermers, McGilchrist, Fenner, Wilson, & McGreevy, 2023; Longland & Byrd, 2006; Molle, Cannas, & Gregorini, 2022) and other orthopaedic diseases, caused by the increased ossification rate associated with faster growth (horses: Donabédian et al., 2006). Furthermore, frothy bloat can occur due to a large intake of highly digestible proteins, especially present in legumes (e.g. white clover) (Wang, Majak, & McAllister, 2012). Moreover, obesity in equids may contribute to various health and welfare concerns (Rogers, Legg, Gibson, & Gee, 2023), including impaired thermoregulation (horses: Cymbaluk & Christison, 1990), compromised reproductive efficiency (horses: Fitzgerald, Reedy, Sessions, Vick, & Murphy, 2003), increased risk of colic (horses: Garcia-Seco et al., 2005), and susceptibility to laminitis (horses: Field & Jeffcott, 1989; donkeys: Du Toit & Trawford, 2010). When large camelids are imported into regions or countries with abundant, nutrient rich pastures, with poor floristic diversity, the risk of metabolic disorders and obesity increase, as shown by observations made in camel farms in France (Faye, Chacornac, Ratovonahary, & Jouany, 1995).

In some cases, the presence of poisonous plants at pasture is a risk for ruminants and equines, with the ingestion of these plants leading to health issues or even death (Aboling, 2023). Moreover, perennial ryegrass toxicosis (PRGT) is a well-known problem in ruminants grazing on fungal endophyte-infected (by *Neotyphodium lolii*) perennial ryegrass (e.g. in alpacas: Sampaio et al., 2008), with sporadic cases occurring in Europe during summer and autumn seasons. Ergot alkaloids (including ergovaline) in grass and seed are associated with health issue in livestock, and can lead, for example, to decreased feed intake, growth, fertility and reproduction performances (EFSA, 2024). In Africa, toxicity of *Capparis tomentosa* (Idris, Salih, Wahbi, & Abdelgadir, 1979) or *Taccazea yototacolla* (Mekonnen & Faye, 1986) was reported in grazing camels.

6.2 Thermal stress

Exposure to adverse weather conditions, such as wind and rain (and the associated muddy conditions) can cause poor welfare (cattle: EFSA, 2009; Mee & Boyle, 2020; Moons, Sonck, & Tuytens, 2014) resulting in less time feeding, less time spent lying and more standing (cattle: Schütz, Clark, Cox, Matthews, & Tucker, 2010; Tucker et al., 2007). Severe cold, snow, rain and wind conditions have also been associated with pregnancy toxemia (metabolic disorder due to energy deficit), probably due to the difficulties of the animals to eat under these conditions (sheep and goats: Silva et al., 2022). Therefore, there is a concrete possibility that the animals may suffer as a result of cold conditions, with reports of higher mortality rates, especially in young or sheared adult sheep (Maurya, Sejian, & Naqvi, 2013; Tüfekci & Sejian, 2023; Verbeek et al., 2012). Higher mortality rates of young animals during the winter season can be due to poor quality milk from malnourished mothers (deer: Lovari et al., 2014).

Animals suffer as a result of hot conditions, which can, for example causes tremors, increased breathing rate and apathy in donkeys (Pritchard, Barr, & Whay, 2006; Zakari, Ayo, Kawu, & Rekwot, 2015). Heat stress generally reduce feed intake of animals (cattle: Chen, Thorup, Kudahl,

& Østergaard, 2024; goats: Lu, 1989; sheep: Marai, El-Darawany, Fadiel, & Abdel-Hafez, 2007). In addition, heat stress leads to reproduction problems (such as reduced follicular growth, fertility rate and embryo survival and development) (sheep: Sawyer & Narayan, 2019; goats: El Sabry & Almasri, 2023; Ozawa et al., 2005; Sejian, Bhatta, Gaughan, Dunshea, & Lacetera, 2018) and prenatal and postnatal offspring development problems (resulting in higher mortality rate or low birth weight) (sheep: Devi, Shinde, Kumar, & Sahoo, 2020; Marai et al., 2007; Tüfekci & Sejian, 2023).

The thermal stresses mentioned above may lead to varying degrees of adverse effects, depending on the typical weather conditions of the country and whether mitigation measures, such as shelters (natural and/or artificial), are present. Shelters represent a key resource for animals during adverse weather conditions (both extreme hot and cold conditions), as well as during extreme events (e.g. strong winds, storms). During the summer, non-sheltered sheep had a respiration rate 56% higher than those sheltered, probably due to direct solar radiation exposition. In a study on equines, higher rectal temperature, respiration rate, and skin temperature have been described and animals showed more sweating than those in the shaded area (Holcomb, Tucker, & Stull, 2014). Similarly, the increase in respiration rate (sign of heat stress) in high ambient temperature was greater for cows that were not in shade than those in shade (Van Laer et al., 2015). The use of shelters increases when the outside weather conditions are cold, rainy, and windy (outside the thermal comfort zone), as shown by Mejdell, Bøe, & Jørgensen (2020) in horses. Cows with free access to outdoor areas avoid being outside during rainy periods (Charlton, Rutter, East, & Sinclair, 2011; Legrand, Von Keyserlingk, & Weary, 2009; Smid, Burgers, Weary, Bokkers, & von Keyserlingk, 2019). Furthermore, horses use shelters more on days when there is high insect activity (Christensen et al., 2022). Camels also seem to prefer shade during hot weather, and access to shaded areas has a positive effect on their behaviours (i.e. more time in recumbency and ruminating compared to camels without shade areas) (Zappaterra, Menchetti, Nanni Costa, & Padalino, 2021).

For more details about thermal stress, see our review on thermal comfort in ruminants and equines (Karatzia, Vecchio, Sossidou, & Veissier, 2025).

6.3 Walking-related stress and locomotory disorders

Several authors have explained how poorly maintained walking tracks/roads, and long distances walked are major risk factors for lameness (cattle: Chesterton, Pfeiffer, Morris, & Tanner, 1989). Long distances walked may also reduce the time available for resting and grazing, and may be associated with potential fatigue (cattle: Coulon, Pradel, Cochard, & Poutrel, 1998; Mee & Boyle, 2020). Furthermore, other authors pointed out that adverse effects associated with long walks increase in cases of extreme heat conditions, which can expose animals to feeding, water and walking-related stress (sheep: Sejian et al., 2016; Tüfekci & Sejian, 2023).

6.4 Health disorders and poor management risks

The inspection and health management of animals are inevitably more complex in pasture, due to the large spaces available to free-ranging animals and, consequently, the challenges

encountered in capturing them for potential medical interventions, emergency treatments and the long distances that must be covered for a complete inspection of the animals.

Several authors describe the widespread and common issues associated with bacterial, viral, and endo- and ectoparasitic infections, that may require careful management to ensure adequate disease prevention (cattle: Bennema et al., 2011; Gerry, 2018; Mee & Boyle, 2020; llamas and alpacas: Hertzberg & Kohler, 2006). For example, gastrointestinal parasites are a major health problem in small ruminants, especially at pasture (Torres-Acosta & Hoste, 2008). Animals infected with gastrointestinal parasites usually decrease their voluntary feed intake (i.e. anorexia in sheep and goats: Silva et al., 2022; Sykes & Coop, 2001). Ectoparasites can also represent a welfare issue at pasture. For instance, annoyance, pain and disease can be due to ticks, as they act as vectors of serious diseases (e.g. babesiosis, anaplasmosis) (Zintl et al., 2017) or nonbiting flies (face fly) that, for example, can spread pinkeye (cattle: Denning, Washburn, & Watson, 2014; Gerry, 2018; Perttu et al., 2020), nasopharyngeal myiasis caused by *Cephalopina titillators* (camels: Khater, Ramadan, & Mageid, 2013), or mastitis (cattle: Mee & Boyle, 2020). Respiratory diseases (e.g. caused by bovine herpes viruses) (cattle: Mee & Boyle, 2020) can also be spread through direct contact with other herds.

In addition, difficulties in animal management can be reflected by reduced colostrum intake with consequent underfeeding and higher neonatal mortality risks due to extensive systems (sheep and goats: Silva et al., 2022). Early signs of poor welfare are more difficult to detect due to the large spaces in which the animals are located. A final consideration for animals kept on pasture is the reduced interaction with humans (Aubé et al., 2022). For example, in the study of Battini, Andreoli, Barbieri, & Mattiello (2011), the avoidance distance of dairy cows was higher after the grazing season presumably due to lower contacts with humans during this period.

7 Recommendations to ensure adequate access to pasture

Based on the knowledge previously described, the following recommendations should be considered:

7.1 Feed and water

Ensure there is adequate grass for the animals, considering quantity and quality. Consider necessary supplementation with forage and/or concentrates and minerals if needed (season, type of animals, e.g. lactating animals). Body condition scoring could be used to assess proper feed intake.

Check that animals have easy access to clean and sufficient water sources. Distances of the grazing area to the water points should not exceed 250 m (Phillips, 2008; RSPCA (Royal Society for the Prevention of Cruelty to Animals), 2023); preferably less than 150 m (Coimbra, Machado Filho, & Hötzel, 2012).

In high-quality pastures (especially at the beginning of spring in Europe), grazing time can be limited and should be supplemented by providing hay and straw indoors, especially for large camels (Faye, Konuspayeva, & Magnan, 2023).

7.2 Natural or artificial shelters

Assess whether there are natural or artificial shelters available to protect animals from adverse weather conditions, such as extreme hot or cold conditions and severe weather events like heavy rain, strong winds, etc. Contrary to popular belief, it is necessary to provide shelter to animals from regions with strong sunshine during the hottest hours of the day and during humid periods (e.g. camelids: Zappaterra et al., 2021).

7.3 Disease prevention

Evaluate the general health and health management plans (e.g. parasites control, mineral supplementation, vaccination, lameness management) for the animals and verify that veterinary care is provided as needed. Ensure that a sick pen is provided. Also, ensure that there are enough trained caretakers and the frequency of daily inspections (at least once a day), and that biosecurity measures are taken when appropriate.

7.4 Walking tracks and roads

Ensure walking tracks/roads are well maintained, have a layer of fine dressing material that is free of sharp stones, rocks, slippery surface, and excessively muddy or water-logged areas. Do not rush animals while herding them. Avoid walking long distances.

8 Gaps in knowledge and further studies needed

In general, studies are lacking on the health and welfare of small ruminants, deer and camelids at pasture, whether for the risks (health, nutrition, behaviours) or the benefits. Even for cattle and horses for which more studies are available, there is a lack of data on how to properly manage the risks identified. Moreover, protocols to assess animal welfare at pasture do not exist (such as the Welfare Quality Protocol for indoor cattle) but would be helpful to improve the welfare of ruminants and equines kept at pasture in Europe.

9 Conclusions

There is a tendency in Europe to decrease pasture access for dairy ruminants. According to the scientific literature, pasture access and grazing are mainly beneficial for those animals, as it allows them to express natural feeding and exploration behaviours, to improve some health parameters and to presumably experience more positive emotions (linked to e.g. positive social interactions, comfort, choice in feed). However, when providing access to pasture, critical aspects such as the quality/quantity of the feed, ambient conditions, walking distance, type of soil and parasites infestations must be carefully managed in order to provide the best outdoor conditions for animals.

10 References

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About EURCAW Ruminants & Equines

EURCAW Ruminants & Equines is the third European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare. It focuses on ruminant and equine welfare and legislation, and covers the entire life cycle from birth to the end of life. EURCAW Ruminants & Equines' main objective is a harmonised compliance with EU legislation regarding welfare in EU Member States. This includes:

- Directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept on farms;
- Regulations 1/2005/EC and 1099/2009/EC concerning their protection during transport and slaughter;
- Directive 2010/63/EU concerning the protection of animals used for scientific purposes;
- Directive 2008/119/EC laying down minimum standards for the protection of calves.

EURCAW Ruminants & Equines supports:

- Inspectors of Competent Authorities (CAs);
- Ruminant and equine welfare policy workers;
- Bodies supporting CAs with scientific expertise, training, and communication.

Website and contact

EURCAW Ruminants & Equines' website offers relevant and actual information to support enforcement of ruminant and equine welfare legislation.

We offer a 'Questions to EURCAW' service for official inspectors, policy workers, and other personnel providing advice or support for official controls of ruminant and equine welfare in the EU. For more information go to <https://www.eurcaw-ruminants-equines.eu/questions-to-eurcaw/>.

Activities of EURCAW Ruminants & Equines

- Coordinated Assistance
Providing support, networking and Questions to EURCAW;
- Welfare indicators, Assessment & Best Practice
Identifying animal welfare indicators, including animal based, management based and resource-based indicators, that can be used to verify compliance with the EU legislation;
- Scientific and technical studies
Preparing Scientific Reviews of knowledge on welfare topics and identify research needs;
- Training
Developing training materials and training standards for official inspectors;
- Communication and Dissemination
Increasing awareness of our outputs via the website, twitter, and newsletter;

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